

Supplementary files of chapter 5 Peppermint oil and sweets in pediatric irritable bowel syndrome and functional abdominal pain: a trial-based economic evaluation.

Supplementary figures

Supplementary figure 1. Cost-effectiveness plane: unadjusted analysis.

A. Peppermint oil vs Placebo

B. Peppermint sweets vs Placebo

Supplementary figure 2. Cost-effectiveness plane: effectiveness measured as proportion responders.

Supplementary figure 3. Cost-effectiveness plane: healthcare perspective.

Supplementary figure 4. Cost-effectiveness plane: per protocol analysis.

Supplementary figure 5. Cost-effectiveness plane: complete case analysis.

Supplementary figure 6. Cost-effectiveness plane of peppermint oil compared with placebo: stratified according to age.

Supplementary figure 7. Cost-effectiveness plane of peppermint oil compared with placebo: stratified according to diagnosis (IBS or FAP-NOS).

Supplementary tables

Supplementary table 1. Unit costs.

Source		
Costs per consultation		Costs
Medical specialist	DMC	
Emergency care	DMC	276,64
General practitioner	DMC	33,10
General practice mental health worker	DMC	22,36
Physiotherapist	DMC	41,70
Exercise therapist	DMC	46,01
Osteopath	Assumed to be comparable to physiotherapist	46,01
Psychologist	DMC ^a	129,74
School doctor	Assumed to be comparable to general practitioner	33,10
Dietician	DMC	26,48
Complementary and alternative therapist	Based on study by Hoekman et al.[8]	84,21
Costs per hospital admission per day	DMC	690,53
Average distance to		Distance in km
Hospital, outpatient clinic	DMC	4,8/iMCQ questionnaire
Emergency care	DMC	7,1
General practitioner	DMC	1
General practice mental health worker	DMC	1
Physiotherapist	Based on study by Hoekman et al.[8]	2,2
Exercise therapist	Assumed to be comparable to physiotherapist	2,2
Osteopath	Assumed to be comparable to physiotherapist	2,2
Psychologist	Assumed to be comparable to physiotherapist	2,2
School doctor	Based on study by Hoekman et al.[8]	1,7
Dietician	Assumed to be comparable to physiotherapist	2,2
Complementary and alternative therapist	Assumed to be comparable to physiotherapist	2,2
Travel costs per km		Costs per km

Car	DMC	0,26
Parking costs	DMC	3,92
Public transport	DMC	0,21
Taxi (+starting costs)	DMC	2,47 (3,36)
Ambulance costs	DMC	528
Productivity and school costs		Costs
Productivity loss, hour	DMC	42,76
Education, primary school, day	DMC	55,86
Education, secondary school, day	DMC	81,36

▫ *Based on first line psychology*

Supplementary table 2. Results of the exploratory subgroup analyses

	Incremental costs (95% CI) ^a	Incremental effects (95% CI) ^a	ICER	NE ^b	SE ^b	SW ^b	NW ^b	pCE
								10,000
Age	≤ 12 years (primary school)							
Peppermint oil	240 (-122, 602)	0.005 (-0.001, 0.011)	50,823	85.4	8.9	0.3	5.3	15.8
Peppermint sweets	230 (-82, 543)	0.004 (-0.003, 0.010)	60,801	81.0	6.4	0.6	11.9	12.6
	> 12 years (secondary school)							
Peppermint oil	75 (-294, 443)	-0.003 (-0.010, 0.004)	Dominated ^c	10.9	7.1	25.4	56.7	29.5
Peppermint sweets	121 (-287, 529)	0.001 (-0.006, 0.007)	218,315	38.6	19.5	9.3	32.6	29.7
IBS or FAP - NOS	IBS							
Peppermint oil	-7 (-323, 308)	0.003 (-0.004, 0.009)	Dominant ^d	37.9	41.3	9.8	11.0	58.0
Peppermint sweets	29 (-299, 357)	0.004 (-0.002, 0.011)	6,635	49.9	41.1	2.5	6.5	53.3
	FAP-NOS							
Peppermint oil	385 (-27, 743)	-0.001 (-0.008, 0.006)	Dominated ^c	42.1	1.0	0.8	56.1	2.1
Peppermint sweets	249 (-113, 610)	0.000 (-0.007, 0.007)	705,197	48.3	6.1	3.0	42.5	10.3

Costs in euros, effect in QALYs gained, unless otherwise indicated.

^a Bootstrapped confidence intervals.

^b Percentage of bootstrapped cost-effect pairs located in this quadrant of the CE plane.

^c ICER is not calculated because the intervention is both more expensive and less effective as placebo (dominated strategy).

^d ICER is not calculated because the intervention is both less costly and more effective as placebo (dominant strategy).

ICER, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio; NE, north east; NW, north west; pCE, probability that the intervention is cost-effective as compared to placebo given a willingness-to-pay threshold of €10,000/QALY; QALY, quality-adjusted life year; SE, south east; SW, south west.